

Analysis of Learning Models in Film

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Abstract

As holders of an important role in learning, teachers and prospective teachers should be equipped with competence in solving problems in the classroom. In the film "Freedom Writer" there are several scenes that we can sample to improve competence in solving problems in class. In the movie "Freedom Writer" the problem that arises in class is about racism. The purpose of this film is to identify problems that can occur in the classroom and how to overcome them. The method used in this research is a two-stage signification semiotic analysis method by Roland Barthes. The main data is obtained based on observations by watching the film Freedom Writers, then the author will make thorough and in-depth observations of each shot per scene. Next, the writer will identify the dialogue and visual images that can represent and describe the social message being studied. Secondary data will be obtained through literature study using reading literature, reading books and scientific works that are related and relevant to the object of research to be studied. The conclusion of this study is the meaning of the educational message contained in the film Freedom Writers which is an example of how teachers or prospective teachers are able to solve problems in the classroom. This film also teaches the value of anti-racism and violence, the value of cooperation, and the value of justice.

Keywords: *Teacher; Racism; Problem Solving*

Introduction

Film is a cinematographic work that can function as a tool for cultural education or cultural education. Thus, films are also effective in conveying cultural values. Meanwhile, Ardianto and Lukiaty (2007) stated that films can contain informative, educative, and even persuasive functions. Movies are part of our daily life in many ways. Even the way we talk is heavily influenced by film metaphors.

Films are not merely merchandise but a means of information and education. Like literary works that have useful and entertaining functions, films are artistic works. But film is also a synthetic work (a blend of various branches of art) and a collective work. The film involves the artists from various branches of art, such as fine arts, design arts, music arts, acting, literary arts, dance arts, and others, in addition to involving technology experts such as; expert electronics, cameras, computers, and other advanced technologies in displaying action scenes and other attractive scenes with charming tricks. Therefore, it would not be an exaggeration to say that film and other types of cinema are the most complex artistic media.

According to Littlejohn, (2009: 53) in his book *Communication Theories of Human Communication* edition 9, Semiotics aims to find out the meanings contained in a sign or interpret these meanings so that it is known how communicators construct messages. Semiotics is a theory that gives signs that have meaning and these signs are then interpreted as a form of understanding life. Humans through their minds interact by using signs as tools for various purposes, one of these goals is to communicate with others as a form of adaptation to the environment. The semiotic theory of Charles Sanders Peirce is often called the "Grand Theory" because the idea is comprehensive, a structural description of all significations, Peirce wants to identify the basic particles of sign and recombine the components in a single structural (Indiwan, 2011: 13). Peirce explains about the three elements of a sign that are interconnected, namely the representamen, the object, and the interpretant.

Moral is an act or behavior of humans as humans in terms of good and bad in terms of habits, good and bad behavior, regarding what should and should not be done related to the ultimate goal of human life. In a film can be taken from the reality of everyday life or from novels that are popular at the time, besides that films can also contain moral elements in society that can be seen from the good or bad relationship with the purpose of human life based on natural law.

The film *Freedom Writer* provides a lot of motivation in it. This film raises a lot of social issues where there are still many racism problems that occur even in the classroom, which means that racism occurs at a young age. This film explores the struggles of a teacher who faces cases of racism and gang wars that occur in the classroom. One day Erin tries to ask her students - her students to write down anything in the diary that is distributed to each student - her students. In the book students can write down what they feel and experience, and this method works. Erin reads these books and Erin understands that she has to make her students realize that war between gangs is not everything. Through a very unique way of teaching, by trying to make his students realize that with education they can achieve a better life.

The researcher is interested in choosing the object of research in the *Freedom Writer* film, because the researcher is interested in the attitude, sacrifice, and struggle of a teacher named Erin Gruwell who fights for the war between gangs in the class she teaches to stop. Erin Gruwell tries various learning methods so that his students feel comfortable and eager to learn again. Therefore, researchers are interested in conducting research with the theme of research "analysis of learning methods" in the film *Freedom Writer*.

Research Method

Types of Research

The research method used in this study uses the semiotic analysis method of Two Stage Significance by Roland Barthes. Semiotic analysis of Roland Barthes examines signs and how they work, this thinking is based on Saussure's thinking about signs which he divides into signifiers and signifieds, where Barthes' analysis is divided into several stages of analysis, namely denotation, connotation, and myth. The denotation system is the first level signification system, which consists of a chain of signifiers and signifieds, namely the relationship of the materiality of the signifier and the abstract concept behind it. According to Barthes, at the denotation level, language generates social codes whose sign meanings immediately appear to the surface based on the relationship between the signifier and the signified. On the Contrary, at the connotation level, language presents codes whose sign meanings are hidden (implicit). This hidden meaning is a meaning which, according to Barthes, is an area of ideology or mythology (Sobur 2009:69).

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The author deliberately limits the shooting of scenes in the film Freedom Writer which have moral messages and symbols to represent how a teacher deals with issues that occur in the classroom. Research Instrument

The main data is obtained based on observations by watching the film Freedom Writers, then the author will make thorough and in-depth observations of each shot per scene. Next, the writer will identify the dialogue and visual images that can represent and describe the social message being studied. Secondary data will be obtained through literature study using reading literature, reading books and scientific works that are related and relevant to the object of research to be studied.

Research Techniques

The research technique consists of two, namely 1) Observation is to make observations directly and not tied to the object of research and the unit of analysis by watching and observing carefully the dialogues, as well as the scenes in the film "Freedom Writer". Then record, select and analyze according to the research model used. 2) Communication studies (document research), where the author collects data through reviewing and reviewing various literatures that

are relevant to research material to be used as argumentation material, such as DVD films, archives, magazines, newspapers, lecture notes, internet and others. other.

Data Analysis Techniques

After the primary and secondary data are collected, they are then clarified according to the research questions that have been determined. After the data is clarified, data analysis is carried out to determine the learning method contained in the film "Freedom Writer".

Result and Discussion

In analyzing the film Freedom Writers, the researcher used denotative and connotative semiotic analysis from Roland Barthes. Denotative analysis is in the form of elaboration of the actual meaning of the signs displayed by a series of scenes, such as dialogues said by characters or other examples, namely the color of clothes that the characters in the film like. While the connotative analysis is in the form of elaboration of hidden meanings, or in this study the connotative meaning is an educative message which is interpreted in each series of scenes in the film Freedom Writers. Jucius (1991) mentions motivation as an activity to encourage someone or oneself to take a desired action. Motivation has a strategic role in one's learning activities. No one learns without motivation, no motivation means no learning activities. Therefore, a teacher must be able to instill motivation in his students. As shown in the following scene.

The denotative meaning in this scene is that Erin Gruwell, who knows the conditions of gang violence experienced by his students, holds a drinking and toast event with his students to invite them to change for the better by leaving the racial strife they experience. He also gave gifts in the form of books that would inspire his students to learn. The connotative meaning in this scene is that a teacher must have a great motivation like Erin Gruwell to motivate and encourage the students of class 203 in the new semester to become a motivator in him. In this scene, Erin motivates her students so that their students have the enthusiasm to change themselves for the better.

Conclusion and Suggestion

Based on the results of the research and discussion in the previous chapter about the substance of the message of the Freedom Writers film and the development of learning scenarios using the Freedom Writers film, it can be concluded that this film has many moral messages, one of which is that we are able to learn learning methods that can be used if there is an issue of racism in society. Class

Reference

Barthes, R. (2012). Pendekatan Semiotika Model Roland Barthes dalam Karya Sastra Prancis. Seminar Nasional FIB UI, 1–15.

- Denny Pratama. (2014). Makna Pesan Sosial Dalam Film *Freedom Writers* (Analisis Semiotika). 109.
- Gide, A. (1967). 濟無 No Title No Title No Title. *Angewandte Chemie International Edition*, 6(11), 951–952., 1989, 5–24.
- Juliani, R. (2018). Analisis Pesan Anti Rasisme Dalam Film *Dear White People*. SOURCE: *Jurnal Ilmu Komunikasi*, 4(1), 38–49. <https://doi.org/10.35308/source.v4i1.737>
- Pricillia, M. (2017). Representasi Nilai Diskriminasi Rasial Dalam Film “*Twelve Years a Slave*” Karya Steve Mcqueen. *EJournal Ilmu Komunikasi*, 5(1), 260–271.
- Rita, V. N. (2015). Rasisme Dalam Film *99 Cahaya Di Langit Eropa Part 1* (Analisis Semiotika Dalam Film *99 Cahaya Di Langit Eropa Part 1*). *Komuniti*, VII(2), 79–91.
- Sancoyo, G. L. A. (2018). Analisis Substansi Pesan Edukatif Film “*Freedom Writers*” Dan Pengembangan Skenario Pembelajarannya Untuk Perkuliahan Mata.
- Setiawan, F. B., Hadi, I. P., & Budiana, D. (2018). Penggambaran Kekerasan Rasisme Dalam Film *Detroit*. *Jurnal E-Komunikasi*, 6(2), 1–10. <http://publication.petra.ac.id/index.php/ilmu-komunikasi/article/view/8290>
- Syahri, D. (2011). Analisis Semiotik Film “*Freedom Writers*.” http://repository.uinjkt.ac.id/dspace/bitstream/123456789/2872/1/DAHLIANA_SYAHRI-FDK.PDF

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